

The Successful Implementation of Public Service Agency in Politeknik Negeri Bandung Through Identification of Business Units

Mia Rosmiati¹, Hastuti², Benny Barnas³, Deni Mulyana⁴

1,2,3(Accounting Department/Politeknik Negeri Bandung, Indonesia)

4(Mechanical Engineering Department/Politeknik Negeri Bandung, Indonesia)

Abstract: Article 1 point (1) of Law no. 23 of 2005 concerning the Financial Management of Public Service Agencies states that the Public Service Agency (BLU) is an agency within the government that was formed to provide services to the community in the form of providing goods and/or services that are sold without prioritizing seeking profit and in carrying out their activities based on the principle of efficiency, and productivity. This study aims to identify business units to support the implementation of the Public Service Agency (BLU) at Politeknik Negeri Bandung (Polban) which will be implemented starting in 2023. The method used in this study is a qualitative method whiches the researcher seeks to explore and collect data through in-depth interviews with informan who are closely related to the theme of this research. The results of the study indicate that by identifying and maximizing business units that have been partly owned by Polban, it will support the implementation of BLU become more focused so that Polban could become an independent university and could improve services to students, to the public and to the community. Further more Polban could increase its ranking both on a national and international scale.

Keywords: government; public service agency; public service

I. Introduction

Politeknik Negeri Bandung (Polban) is one of the State Universities (PTN) that will implement PK BLU management and is preparing various facilities and infrastructure that support the implementation of PK BLU. The application of PK BLU at PTN is expected to be a renewal of government sector management and it will improve services to the community. In the PK BLU management system, flexibility is given to implement sound business practices based on good management principles in the context of providing quality and sustainable services, and in an effort to promote public welfare and educate the nation's life [1]. This is in line with [2] which states that they carry out their functions and roles clearly and effectively, and promote the values of the entire organization. The government seeks to implement GCG in PTN by establishing BLU which aims to improve the quality of government services to the community, thus government institutions are more free to design financial policies in a healthy and independent manner in the fields of operations and management and increase productivity [3].The BLU Financial Management Pattern (PPK) is a pattern of financial management in public service organizations/agencies (public service agencies) that provides flexibility in the form of the flexibility to implement sound business practices to improve services to the community [4]. This is in line with what is being done by the private sector where the main factor in the success of managing an organization is to improve services to customers or service users. As quoted from [5] which states that public service organizations have come under increasing pressure from deregulation and the continuous comparison with the

private sector. They have made considerable efforts to improve their efficiency, to reduce costs by downsizing and rationalization, by introducing new managerial concepts and tools and by being more responsive to citizens. In order to realize a pattern of financial management that is more flexible and can improve services to the community, Polban have decided to change the status from PTN Satker to PTN with PK BLU. This new status will make Polban become independent PTNs by changing the pattern of asset management, governance and human resources that will support the pattern of financial management in accordance with the PK BLU. This is in accordance with research conducted by [6] which states that despite being supported by revenue, BLU is also supported by facilities and infrastructure in the form of assets owned. These three aspects are important for BLU in order to improve the quality of public services and the quality of BLU as an institution reflected in the BLU's accreditation. The implementation of PK BLU in Polban in reality still faces obstacles in the field of asset management where assets are one of the important elements in this PK BLU because these assets will become the business unit that will be the basis for managing BLU Polban. Therefore, the implementation of this BLU PK policy must be carefully prepared, especially in managing its assets which are the source of BLU income.

The implementation of PK BLU is the right way to carry out a correct policy in order to achieve a goal that has been approved or set by policy makers [7]. The goal to be achieved by the government in terms of implementing PK BLU is so that PTN can further improve services to the community and can be independent and flexible in managing their finances. In addition, policy implementation refers to actions to achieve a goal that has been approved in a decision. This is an action to change a decision into an operational pattern and to achieve a pre-agreed change [8]. Polban as part of government-owned educational institutions has an obligation to provide good public services to students and its in line with the concept that policy implementation is carried out by the state through a government agency, because this is an effort by the government in carrying out its main task, namely providing services. public to society [9].

To support the policy implementation process, there are 4 (four) determining factors, namely:

1. Communication has an important role as a reference for implementing policies and this communication is also stated by orders from superiors to policy implementers, so that communication must be stated clearly, quickly and consistently.
2. Resources, not only regarding human resources but also include the capabilities of other resources that support the policy, including sources of funds and assets.
3. The disposition and attitude of the implementer is needed to implement the policy. Executors must know and be able to carry out orders from superiors.
4. The organizational structure of the bureaucracy, has an impact on the implementation of policies in the sense that the implementation of policies will not succeed if there are weaknesses in the structure. In this case there are 2 general characteristics of the bureaucracy, the use of routine attitudes and procedures and the transformation of accountability among organizational units [10].

The transfer of management and financial management from the Satker to the BLU certainly requires the full participation and support of all elements in Polban, especially those from the ranks of the business units, because this change is hard to be implemented. The business unit itself is the core of the implementation of PK BLU so it is hoped that Polban can maximize their potential through the utilization of business units.

To realize these expectations, this study aims to analyze the role and potential of the business units owned by Polban so that the results of this analysis will produce a pattern of policies/methods that can be applied in an effort to maximize the role of business units in realizing the implementation of PK BLU.

II. Methods

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive type of research. The qualitative approach was chosen because the research has the intent to explore and understand the meanings ascribed to social or humanitarian problems. This qualitative research process involves important efforts, such as asking questions and procedures, collecting specific data from the participants, analyzing the data inductively and interpreting the meaning of the data.

While descriptive research was chosen because this type of research tries to find an appropriate and sufficient description of all activities, processes, and objects of research.

Data collection techniques are things that need to be done in research because data collection techniques are ways that help researchers collect data needed in research. In qualitative research there are four ways of data collection techniques, namely participant observation, in-depth interviews, documentation studies, and a combination of the three or triangulation [11]. Observation is a method of systematic analysis and recording of behavior by observing or observing individuals or groups directly. Thus, this technique is used to deepen the knowledge of researchers in knowing the general picture regarding the PK BLU implementation plan and the obstacles faced in the Polban environment. Interviews are one of the most widely used and basic methods for obtaining qualitative data. This technique is used to find out clearly, in detail and in depth about the actual situation, namely by conducting interviews with various sources that can provide information about the general picture or data regarding the objective conditions regarding the implementation of PK BLU Polban. The determination of the interviews with the subjects in this study was carried out based on consideration by choosing subjects who were more understanding and related to the information to be collected. Qualitative research is research that is grounded research, so that the number of informants can still increase along with the skills of the research instrument at the time of data collection.

Other sources of information in research can be obtained from documents. The process of collecting documents is carried out continuously both to triangulate the data obtained from interview and observation techniques and to explore data that are difficult to convey through interviews. Triangulation is a data collection technique that combines several data collection techniques and existing sources.

Results and Discussion

Politeknik Negeri Bandung (Polban) is in the process of implementing the Public Service Agency in its financial management. This is necessary to be done so that Polban can further improve services to the community and can be more competitive with other universities in the field of Human Resources which is one of the determining factors for success in implementing a policy. This is in line with the statement from [2] that The government has full responsibility for the implementation of higher education in Indonesia to create competitive human resources. There are four factors that determine the success of policy implementation [10], namely:

a. Communication

Communication has an important role as a reference for policy implementation and this communication is also stated by orders from superiors to policy implementers, so that communication must be stated clearly, quickly and consistently. In terms of changing the pattern of financial management of Polban from Satker to BLU, a good form of communication that is carried out in two directions will create a common understanding of this change between top management and their subordinates. Information regarding the change in management patterns from Satker to BLU has been communicated by management to the entire Polban academic community since 2011 but at that time the enthusiasm to change from Satker to BLU was still not the main goal of Polban. Then over time and the law regarding the implementation of the BLU has been enacted, the Polban continues the agenda that was delayed and begins to re-plan the team work program that takes care of moving from the satker to PK BLU through various socializations initiated by the management and the BLU team such as seminars and FGDs where the implementation involved parties from outside the Polban, namely the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Education and Culture because these two ministries were responsible for the birth of universities with BLU financial management patterns. This is very important to be carried out by top management because this BLU policy will involve all the Polban academic community so that when the time comes for this policy to be implemented, it is hoped that all parties can provide maximum support to the Polban institution so that the objectives of implementing this BLU PK policy can be achieved.

b. Resources

These resources are the main topic in this research because the availability of these resources will be the reference for this BLU PK policy that can be implemented properly. Resources in the BLU financial pattern are not only related to human resources but also include the capabilities of other resources that support this policy, including sources of funds and assets. When Polban has become a university by implementing a BLU financial management pattern, Polban can be more independent in managing their finances, including Polban can explore the potential of their assets in order to generate income that will be used to finance the institution. The initial step taken by the researchers was to collect secondary data regarding information containing potential assets or business prospects owned by Polban which could be converted into rupiah.

Polban has 10 majors and 1 postgraduate, each of which has potential assets to be used as business units or business prospects. Basically, business for Polban as a higher education institution has 2 business groups:

1. The use and utilization of every element in Higher Education includes the Tridharma of Higher Education which includes education and teaching, research and community service (PkM). As a higher education organization, the Polban business is an activity to implement the Tridharma of Higher Education, which includes education, research, and community service activities. All activities and programs prepared for the implementation of these activities are outlined in the institutional strategic plan. Therefore, the targets, activity plans, and programs of the 2020-2024 Strategic Plan are the basis of the Polban business plan for the 2022-2026 period covering strategic objectives, strategic objectives, and program objectives. Program and activity strategies and performance indicators are prepared in accordance with the targets that have been set for each strategic target and refer to the Main Activity Indicators (IKU) of the Ministry of Education and Culture [12]. The explanation of this first point can be seen in the following tables.

Table 1
Diversity of Business Prospects from 2022 to 2026

Business Units	Type of Business Service	Type of Operation	
		Use	Utilization
Education	Reg Class	√	√
	Industrial Class	-	√
	Training/Certification	√	√
Research	Scientific Study Service for business/community/industry	-	√
PkM	Training/Sertification	√	√
	Consulting Service for Industry	√	√
Physical Assets	Land and Building Utilization	-	√

Source : Document of RBA BLU Polban, 2022

The activities that will be carried out to achieve strategic targets are those related to elements of service, finance, human resources, infrastructure, innovation, and investment. The relationship between each of these elements and the activities to be carried out in achieving strategic business/strategic initiatives that refer to the strategic goals and target indicators is reflected in table 2 below:

Table 2
Polban Business Unit Development Activity Plan

Strategic Target for 2020-2024	Strategic Business Activity	Target for The Next 5 Years					
		Percent	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
1. Improve the quality of learning and student affairs	• Improvement of postgraduate program (Master and Doctoral applied)	%	23,5	24,5	25,5	27,5	32,5
	• Featured study program accreditation						
	• International accreditation for study program						
	• Composing international program and double degree						
	• Implementation of MBKM policy						
2. Improve the quality of vocational institutions	• Administration efficiency	%	3	3	3,5	4	5
	• Implementation modern service (paperless)						
	• Implementation of clean/good governance						
	• Implementation of comprehensive information system management						
	• Increase the average of SAKIP	Predikat	A	A	A	A	A
	• Average value of budget performance	Nilai	94	95	100	100	100
3. Improve the relevance, quality and quantity of resources	• Increase the number of doctoral program for lecturer	%	23,5	24,5	25,5	27,5	32,53
	• Competency improvement for vocational lecturers						
	• Promotions of lecturers						
	• Industrial internship						
	• Improvement of patents and research products						
	• Improving the quality of publications and citations						
	• Study center establishment						
4. Improve the relevance and productivity of research, development, and learning opportunities for the	• Laboratory rejuvenation	%	0,12	0,13	0,15	0,18	0,2
	• Educational collaborations						

community							
5. Improve the innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of IT innovations in new study program for S2/D4/D3 Designing innovative new courses for ICT 	%	36	37	40	45	50

Source: Document of RBA BLU Polban, 2022

In order to achieve the Strategic Goals, Strategic Activities and Targets for the next 5 years, Polban has had a "Superior Program" from non-educational activities which is divided into two major groups, namely (1) engineering-based programs, and (2) managerial-based programs. For engineering-based programs, there are three programs owned by Polban, and for managerial-based superior programs in the form of Business Holding Service with details of superior programs as shown in Table 3 below.

Tabel 3
Polban Featured Program

Featured Program	Program/Activity	Department
1. Engineering Based	• Electrical Training Service	• Electrical Engineering
	• Programable Logic Controller Training	
	• Aeronotical & Mechanical Services Training	• Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering
	• Butt Weld Flate Training	
	• Energy Audit Training and Competency Test	• Energy
	• Operator Boiler Training	
	• Training on Maintenance and Operation of Chemical Instrument Analytical Tools	• Chemical Engineering
	• Testing Services and Data Acquisition	
	• Refrigeration & Air Conditioning Services Training	• Refrigeration Engineering
	• RHVAC Technician Training	
	• Corporate-scale Software Development	• Computer Engineering
	• ICT Management System Design for SIMA	
	• Material Testing	• Civil Engineering
	• Komposite Material Testing	
• Land Testing		
2. Managerial Based	<u>Business Holding:</u>	• Accounting Department
	• Polyclinic	• Business Administration
	• Consulting and Training Center	
	• Rental of Land and Bilding Assets	• English Department
	• Cafetaria	
	• Retail Shop	
	<u>Services:</u>	
	• Business Consultant	
	• Forex Training	
	• Asset Management System Design	
	<u>Training:</u>	

- Accounting
- English Language
- Marketing
- Assets Management
- Business Administration
- Tourism

Source : Document of RBA BLU Polban, 2022

The tridharma of higher education in Polban has been carried out well in the sense that all education staff have carried out teaching and education activities, research and service on a regular basis. Based on table 1 to table 3 above, the three elements in the tridharma can be used as a source of income for Polban after becoming a BLU. With various types of business services in Tridharma, Polban can get a source of income with a large nominal amount of rupiah, so that through the identification of Tridharma elements that can be of commercial value, a real picture can be obtained that Polban can change from Satker to BLU.

1. Utilization of assets (other than Tupoksi Tridharma PT) in the form of land and buildings.

Then the second business group is the use of land and buildings owned by Polban. Based on interviews conducted with officials in charge of land and building management, it is known that Polban has buildings and land that can be taken advantage of financially. The land and buildings can be used as a source of business for Polban if they are properly used. On vacant land, commercial buildings can be made such as cafes, net cafes, or commercial public facilities. Likewise, existing buildings that have not been used optimally can be converted into buildings that can generate profits for Polban.

By identifying the asset resources owned by the Polban, this will quickly realize the implementation of the PK BLU Polban, because the description of the sources of income for Polban has been well identified.

c. Implementing Disposition and Attitude

These two things are very influential in the success of policy implementation and both are absolutely necessary in implementing this BLU financial management policy. Executors must know and be able to carry out orders from superiors. At the initial stage, the director establishes a BLU Polban document drafting team that works synergistically in compiling the BLU PK document in accordance with the stipulated requirements. The deputy director for finance is the head of this team, while the document drafting team consists of lecturers and non-educational staff who have expertise in governance, business units, minimum service standards and finance. In terms of preparing the PK BLU document, the team cooperates with various parties related to these fields and strives to make the maximum contribution to the realization of the Police's goal of becoming a PK BLU. All team members work based on the disposition of top management, namely the director by paying attention to their respective job descriptions so that in the implementation of the program there is no overlap and can minimize risks that will hinder the process of achieving goals, although in every policy there will always be risk opportunities to fail and it is caused by: 1) A policy is not implemented according to the plan, because the parties involved may not be able to work together or the problem being worked on is outside the scope of their power so that the implementation of the policy is difficult to implement; 2) There are external factors that do not support the implementation of the policy, so it does not get optimal results or maybe from the start the policy was not right [13]. Therefore, the disposition and attitude of the implementer is one of the determining factors for the successful implementation of a policy.

a. Bureaucratic Organizational Structure

The last factor that determines the success of implementing a policy has an impact on policy implementation in the sense that policy implementation will not be successful if there are weaknesses in the structure. In this case there are 2 general characteristics of the bureaucracy, the

use of routine attitudes and procedures and the transformation of accountability among organizational units.

Polban has made a draft of the Polban organizational structure if it has implemented the PK BLU which can be seen in the following picture.

Image 1
 Draft Organizational Structure After BLU

Source : Document of Governance BLU Polban, 2022

In the draft Polban organizational structure if it has implemented the PK BLU, it will add 1 important organ, namely the Supervisory Board which has the task of overseeing the process of implementing BLU financial management in all fields which include governance, business units, minimum service standards and finance. This monitoring process is carried out starting from planning, implementation to evaluation. So it is expected that all fields can carry out their main tasks and functions properly and correctly. In this draft BLU PK organizational structure there is a strengthening of one of the important organs in Polban, namely the Internal Monitoring Unit (SPI) where the role of SPI is very large in the implementation of this BLU PK policy, namely as a supervisor who is within the Polban internal tasked with ensuring that all fields have carry out their duties properly and correctly in accordance with applicable laws and regulations without getting intervention from other organs in the organizational structure of PK BLU and are responsible to the Supervisory Board. Strengthening the SPI is appropriate considering that the implementation of a policy will run well if the implementer of the policy has a strong position in the organizational structure.

III. Conclusion

The final conclusion from this research is that the four factors, namely communication, resources, disposition and attitude of the implementers and the organizational structure of the bureaucracy have an important role in the plan for implementing PK BLU Polban. The four of them contribute to the process of achieving the goals of the Polban organization. Through the resource factor, Polban can identify potential assets owned which will be used as a source of financing for PK BLU Polban. It is hoped that all Polban academics can provide maximum

support in the effort to achieve the goals of the Polban organization, to become a university that applies the pattern of financial management of the Public Service Agency.

References

- [1] Waluyo, Budi. "AnalisisPermasalahan Pada Implementasi Pola PengelolaanKeuangan Badan LayananUmum". *JurnalInfoartha* Vol. 3/Tahun XII/2014 (27-38)
- [2] Selvi, U. Kango, "Implementation of Public Service Agency for Good University Governance". *Asia Pacific Journal of Management and Education*, 2020
- [3] FF. Anggriawan, "Good Corporate Governance in The Public Service Agency (case study at University of Brawijaya)" <https://jas.umsida.ac.id>jas>article>, 2010
- [4] Sari, et. al, "AnalisisKomparasi Atas Kinerja dan Keuangan Badan LayananUmumBidangPenyedia Jasa Pendidikan", *Journal of Business Administration* Vol.3/2 Sept 2019 (271-280)
- [5] Pollitt, C. "Structural change and public service performance: International lessons?" *Public Money and Management*, 2009, 29(5), 285–291.
- [6] Amany. et. al. "Peran Pendapatan dan Ukuran Badan LayananUmumTerhadapAkreditasi BLU Pendidikan di Indonesia", *Journal Pajak dan Keuangan Negara*, 2020
- [7] Kadji, Yulianto. "Formulasi Dan ImplementasiKebijakan Publik, Kepemimpinan dan PerilakuBirokrasiDalam Fakta Realitas". 2015, Gorontalo: UNG Press.
- [8] Mulyadi, Deddy. "StudiKebijakan Publik dan Pelayanan Publik: Konsep dan Aplikasi Proses Kebijakan Publik dan Pelayanan Publik". 2015. Bandung : Alfabeta.
- [9] Suharno. "Dasar-Dasar Kebijakan Publik: kajian proses dan analisiskebijakan". 2013. UNY Press.
- [10] Edwards III, George C., "Implementing Public Policy", 2018. Washington DC : Congress Conal Quarterly Press
- [11] Trianto, PengantarPenelitian Pendidikan bagiPengembanganProfesi Pendidikan dan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2020 Jakarta: Kencana.
- [12] Dokumen PK BLU POLBAN, 2022. Politeknik Negeri Bandung.
- [13] Mazmanian, D.A dan Paul A. Sabatier. "Implementation and Public Policy", 2005. London : Scott, Foresman and Company.